

Journal of European **S**ocial Research (**JESR**)

[Volume 4 Issue 1 2025 ISSN:2312-251X]

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This issue of JESR is published within the framework of the Jean Monnet Module “EU Integration of Western Balkans: Patterns and Issues” (WB-EUPath) coordinated by the Center for European Studies at EPOKA University and co-funded by the European Commission.*

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JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN SOCIAL RESEARCH

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THE IMPACT OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN BALKAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The most important growth theories emphasize the substantial role of human capital in economic growth. This article explores the effect of the Human Development Index on GDP growth rate as an indicator of economic growth in the Balkans from 2000 to 2022. Employing panel data analysis, the study observes the impact of HDI on GDP growth, along with several other variables, including FDI-s, Gross Capital Formation, Inflation, Labor, and Trade Openness. The outcomes indicate HDI has a statistically significant positive impact on GDP growth, with HDI contributing to an increase in economic growth. Other variables such as Gross Capital Formation, inflation, and trade openness also demonstrate to have significant positive effects on GDP, while FDI and labour growth exhibit weaker impacts. The model explains about 33% of the variation in GDP, suggesting a moderate level of explanatory power. These findings suggest that promoting human development, as reflected by HDI, has a fundamental role in fostering economic growth in the Balkan countries. This study provides valuable insights for policymakers, emphasizing the significance of focusing on and advancing human development alongside other key economic drivers to support long-term economic growth in Balkan countries.

Keywords: Human Development Index, Economic Growth, Balkans.

Introduction

Economic growth and the Human Development Index are both very important indicators of the wellbeing of a country, even though their focus is distinct. While the Human Development Index measures the most important indicators of human development, such as health, education, and standard of living, economic growth measures the total output volume of a country. Numerous studies attempt to investigate whether these two indicators share a unidirectional or bidirectional causal relationship. Sen (1999) emphasizes the importance of economic growth in enhancing health, education, and the standard of living. Economic growth is crucial for human development, though its impact may be limited if not accompanied by policies targeting human development. In contrast, Rahman, Raja, & Ryan (2020) analyse how human development promotes economic growth over 14 years across 25 developed and 25 developing economies, utilizing a panel data approach. Their findings imply that human development positively affects growth in all countries under study. Ramirez, Ranis, & Stewart (1997) examine the two-way relationship between human development and economic growth over the period 1970-1992 using a cross-country analysis.

Their findings suggest a bidirectional relationship between those two variables; however, the strength of this relationship is related to other factors as well. The authors suggest that based on the relationship, both variables should be promoted, however, the promotion of human development should be prioritized.

The purpose of this article is to examine the impact of human development on economic growth by utilizing the Human Development Index as the independent variable and Foreign Direct Investment, Inflation, Labor, Gross Capital Formation, and Trade Openness as controlling variables.

The motivation behind this study stands on the fact that theories of economic development increasingly emphasize the significance of human capital in fostering economic growth. HDI captures key dimensions of human capital. Furthermore, the Balkans have undergone significant socio-economic transitions, including post-conflict recovery, EU integration efforts, and varying levels of human development. Understanding the region's specific dynamics can provide tailored policy recommendations. Moreover, despite the global recognition of HDI's importance, there is limited empirical research on its specific influence on economic growth in the Balkans. This study aims to provide evidence-based insights for policymakers to prioritize human development alongside traditional economic growth strategies.

Figure 1 gives information regarding the Human Development Index (HDI) scores for nine Balkan countries from 2000 to 2022. There is an upward trend in HDI scores over the years, reflecting improvements in human development in all Balkan countries. Although there are variations in HDI levels, there are regional similarities in development patterns. Slovenia consistently appears to have one of the highest HDI scores in the region throughout the period, suggesting it has achieved relatively better outcomes in human development.

Figure 1. Human Development Index

Source: United Nations Development Programme.

There are slight changes in certain years, possibly due to external economic factors or global events that could have impacted income, health, or education.

Literature Review

Human capital development is acknowledged as a crucial factor in promoting economic growth, especially in developing economies. It incorporates the acquisition and enhancement of skills, education, and health, which improve productivity. Numerous researchers have discovered the connection between human development and economic growth by analysing the Human Development Index published by the United Nations Development Programme.

Ulas & Keskin (2017) use panel data for 20 countries (2010–2014) to confirm a positive relationship between HDI and economic growth. This study highlights the consistent role of human development in fostering GDP growth. Deb (2015) conducted a cross-country analysis and found a strong correlation between HDI and GDP per capita across 140 countries, particularly emphasizing its prominence in low-income economies. This demonstrates that improvements in HDI dimensions (health, education, and income) substantially enhance economic performance.

Elistia & Syahzuni (2018) evaluate the association between the Human Development Index and economic growth in a group of ASEAN countries from 2010 to 2016. For each country included in the study, the authors find a strong significant bidirectional relationship between variables. In the same way, Suri et al. (2011) and Ranis (2004) analyse the two-way linkages of human development with economic growth by applying the panel data approach. The results of their articles indicate that human development plays a crucial role in economic growth and sustainable economic growth.

Hoa, Liem, & Phuoc (2016) examine how the Human Development Index affects growth in 30 economies for the period 1999 until 2014 by using regression analysis. The authors include several controlling variables such as physical capital, social capital, population, openness of economy, inflation, and government spending. The findings suggest that among the significant determinants of economic growth is the human development index as well.

Appiah, Amoasi, & Frowne (2019) examine the effect of the human development index on economic growth and economic development for the period 1990 until 2015 in five African countries by using panel data estimation. The authors use the human development index and other control variables that affect economic growth, such as inflation, government capital formation, foreign direct investments, official development assistance (Aid), and labour. Their findings suggest that the impact of the HDI on economic growth is positive.

Other authors such as Rahman, Raja, & Ryan (2020), also use the HDI to investigate human development's effect on economic growth in 50 developed and developing countries from 2000 until 2014. Other explanatory variables of economic growth are foreign direct investment, trade openness, gross fixed capital formation, and inflation. The authors find that human development is a very significant determinant of economic growth in both groups. Gulcernal (2020) analyses the impact of the Human Development Index on economic growth in 16 middle- and low-income economies for the period from 1990 until 2018 by using a panel data approach. As control variables are used, inflation, government capital, official development assistance, investments, and labour. The outcomes imply a significant positive impact of the Human Development Index on economic growth, emphasizing education and health's contributions to productivity and growth.

Methodology

This article utilized a panel data analysis to assess the relationship between human development and economic growth in nine Balkan countries—Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, and Slovenia—over the period from 2000 to 2022. Kosovo is excluded due to insufficient data. Annual data for this period were sourced from the World Bank Database and the United Nations Development Programme. The dependent variable is the GDP growth rate, representing economic growth, which is explained by the Human Development Index and additional controlling variables, including Foreign Direct Investment, Gross Capital Formation, Inflation, Labor, and Trade Openness. Official Development Assistance is excluded from the analysis, as countries like Bulgaria, Slovenia, Croatia, and Romania have not qualified for such assistance for several years.

The main hypothesis of this study is:

- The re is a statistically significant positive relationship between the Human Development Index and the GDP Growth rate.

Initial tests are conducted to make sure that the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimations are unbiased. Additionally, a multicollinearity analysis is performed to confirm the non-existence of correlations between the independent variables, which helps maintain neutral results. The analysis results in Table 1 indicate that the correlation coefficients are all below 80%, suggesting that the independent variables are not correlated with one another. Consequently, the assumption of no correlation is satisfied.

Table 1. Correlation Matrix

	GDP	FDI	GCAP	HDI	INFL	LABOR	TRADE
GDP	1.000						
FDI	0.170	1.000					
GCAP	0.201	0.226	1.000				
HDI	0.134	0.075	0.187	1.000			
INFL	0.173	0.092	0.008	-0.390	1.000		
LABOR	-0.026	-0.202	-0.175	-0.125	0.100	1.000	
TRADE	0.061	0.220	-0.268	0.058	-0.285	0.1406	1.000

The stationarity of the series is evaluated using Levin, Lin, and Chu. The outcomes in Table 2 specify that series such as GDP Growth rate, Foreign Direct Investment, Human Development Index, and Inflation are stationary at level, and series such as Gross Capital Formation, Labor and Trade Openness are stationary at the first difference.

Table 2. Panel Unit Root test results

Variable	t-stat	Prob	Order of cointegration
GDP	-11.0897	0.0000	I(0)
FDI	-3.98769	0.0000	I(0)
GCAP	-8.59721	0.0000	I(1)
HDI	-20.4945	0.0000	I(0)
INFL	-5.26527	0.0000	I(0)
LABOR	-9.59625	0.0000	I(1)
TRADE	-3.90934	0.0000	I(0)

The Hausman test determines whether a random or fixed effect model is more suitable for the examination. Based on the analysis, the assumption of the zero conditional mean is met as well, as the average value of the error residuals is 1.89E-17. Following this, the correlation of residuals of the error term and the independent variables is examined, and the coefficient value is almost zero.

The results of the heteroskedasticity test indicate that the homoskedasticity assumption is violated. However, the regression does not suffer from serial correlation. As the model is not homoscedastic, a model that adjusts the coefficients' standard errors to solve the heteroskedasticity problem should be used.

Results

The Hausman test results suggest that the fixed effects model is appropriate for this analysis. The equation 1 represents the estimated model, and Table 3 displays the regression estimation obtained running the White diagonal coefficient covariance method.

$$GDP_{it} = -18.89 + 0.068 \cdot FDI_{it} + 21.02 \cdot \Delta GCAP_{it} + 166.91 \cdot HDI_{it} + 0.12 \cdot INFL_{it} + 61.30 \cdot \Delta LABOR_{it} + 10.18 \cdot TRADE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Table 3. Regression Estimation

Dependent Variable: GDP				
White diagonal standard errors & covariance (d.f. corrected)				
Variable	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Stat	Prob.
FDI	0.068	0.0609	1.115	0.2665
D(GCAP)	21.015	8.556	2.456	0.015
HDI	166.911	52.055	3.206	0.0016
INFL	0.121	0.0455	2.663	0.0085
D(LABOR)	61.301	34.296	1.787	0.0756

TRADE	10.178	3.396	2.996	0.0031
C	-18.885	6.802	-2.776	0.0061
R-sqrd	0.331	Adj R-sqrd		0.277
F-stat	6.128	Prob(F-stat)		0

The regression output indicates that the coefficient for HDI is 166.91, t-statistic of 3.20 and a p-value of 0.0016. Considering a p-value that is less than the conventional significance level (0.05), the relationship between HDI and GDP growth is statistically significant. Additionally, the positive coefficient (166.9118) indicates a positive relationship among HDI and GDP growth. Therefore, the findings indicate a statistically significant positive correlation among the Human Development Index and GDP growth rate. The findings are also in accordance with (Deb, 2015; Mustafa, Rizov, & Kernohan, 2017; Gulcemal, 2020) and so forth.

Regarding the other variables, FDI has a positive but statistically insignificant impact on GDP at conventional significance levels ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that changes in FDI may not have a strong immediate influence on GDP in this model. Gross Capital Formation significantly and positively affects GDP ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that an increase in capital growth is associated with higher GDP. Inflation has a positive and significant relationship with GDP ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that modest inflation may correlate with higher GDP, possibly reflecting increased economic activity. Labor growth has a positive but marginally significant effect on GDP ($p \approx 0.075$), which may indicate that changes in the labor force impact GDP, although less strongly than other factors. Trade has a statistically significant positive influence on GDP ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that improved trade is related to higher GDP.

Based on the value of R-squared and Adjusted R-squared, 33% of the variation in GDP is explained by the model, indicating moderate explanatory power. The F-statistics are significant ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that the whole model is statistically significant and that the included variables are jointly significant in explaining GDP.

In summary, HDI, growth in capital, inflation, and trade have significant positive influences on GDP, with the model overall showing a reasonable level of fitness.

Conclusions

This study aimed to analyze the relationship between the Human Development Index (HDI) and economic growth, measured by GDP growth rate, in the Balkan countries from 2000 to 2022. The findings indicate a statistically significant positive correlation between HDI and GDP growth rate. Specifically, the regression results show that a higher HDI is associated with higher GDP growth, with the coefficient for HDI being 166.9118 and a t-statistic of 3.206455, which is highly significant (p-value = 0.0016).

The results also highlight the significant positive effects of other key factors, such as Gross Capital Formation, inflation, and trade, on GDP. The impact of labour growth, while positive, was marginally significant, suggesting that changes in the labour force have a less

pronounced influence on GDP compared to the other variables. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), on the other hand, had a positive but statistically insignificant effect, indicating that FDI might not have an immediate or strong impact on GDP growth in these countries.

The model explains about 33% of the variation in GDP, with an adjusted R-squared of approximately 28%. While this indicates a moderate explanatory power, the overall model is statistically significant, as evidenced by the significant F-statistic. The results confirm the importance of promoting human development alongside other growth factors, such as capital formation, trade, and inflation, to stimulate economic growth in the Balkans.

In conclusion, this study supports the bidirectional relationship between human development and economic growth, being an important driver of sustainable economic growth. Policymakers in the Balkan countries should continue to prioritize human development, alongside fostering trade and capital growth, to further stimulate economic prosperity.

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